

Climate Fiction and the Questions of Viability: An Exploration of Maja Lunde's *The History of Bees*

Jayakrishnan R,
Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
MMNSS College Kottiyam,
Kerala, India.

Abstract: *Climate fiction, popularly known as Cli-fi, is a category of novels that, while maintaining many of the generic characteristics of science fiction from where it originated, experiments with new stylistic and formative ways for effectively negotiating the representative challenges posed by the spatio-temporal aspects of climate change. Academic scholarship that studies climate fiction, while tracing its evolution and development, often delve in two prominent overlapping critical lines – one that explore expectancy, foregrounding what is expected of climate fiction from a critical standpoint to effectively mediate the challenges of climate change and the other that hinges on its limitations as a relatively new category, dependent on the conventional tropes of fiction that has its roots in established generic as well as Western humanistic tradition. This paper, by providing a brief overview of these critical approaches attempts to explore how *The History of Bees* by Maja Lunde with its formative innovation not only negates many of the common critical lines that question the viability of climate fiction in addressing the crises of climate change but also offers itself as a prototype demonstrative of the ways in which science and literature can be effectively brought together without compromising the factual value of science or the emotive capabilities of literature.*

Keywords: **Climate fiction, Cli-fi, Colony collapse disorder (CCD), Maja Lunde, *The History of Bees*.**

The rise of climate fiction or cli-fi as a popular and academic category is inseparable from the unfolding climate crisis of the 21st century. Though the evolution of literary texts that deal with climate change can be traced back to *The Purchase of the North Pole* (1889) by Jules Verne or the novels of J G Ballard like *The Drowned World* (1962), a large repertoire of science fiction novels, described by Jim Clarke using the label ‘proto-climate fiction’ (Trexler and Johns-Putra 186-187) often used settings of catastrophic weather conditions as accidental fall out of scientific or technological attempts to manipulate global climate for the better. Put differently, they were science fiction texts that didn’t deal with the anthropogenic nature of climate change (Goodbody and Johns-Putra 232). This is perhaps better exemplified by Robert Macfarlane’s call in his article for *The Guardian* in 2005 demanding the need of a new category of novels that would break away from the futuristic apocalyptic science fiction tradition and address the issue of climate change in terms of lived human experience.

A survey of scholarly literature on climate fiction during the second and current decade of the 21st century reveal exhortations for the departure of climate fiction from its precursive affiliations with the conventions of science fiction and adopt forms that result from inventive practices like blending of styles and blurring of generic boundaries to adapt to the need of effectively negotiating climate crises. Trexler and Johns-Putra, for instance, asserts this idea when they say that climate change demands innovative plotlines and characterizations “that participate in the global, networked, and controversial nature of climate change”. They demand climate fiction to constitute the relationality of climate change and human experience, to explore “how climate change occurs not just as a meteorological or ecological crisis ‘out there’ but as something filtered through our inner and outer lives” (196). Alison Sperling asserts this when she says that “climate change compels us to reconsider the political underpinnings of our understanding of the world, and therefore also the writing and reading protocols used to narrate it” (13).

The function of responsible writing expected of climate fiction is further reiterated by Goodbody and Johns-Putra who argue that climate fiction needs new imaginaries that could not only meet the challenges posed by climate change in terms of its invisibility and scalar complexities but also bridge the gulf that divides the scientific discourses of climate change and language of literature (229). Antonia Mehnert echoes this notion when she argues that climate fiction can not only represent scientific data in affective registers that offer insight into human subjectivity in the conflicting contexts of climate change but can also shape human understanding of the crises by offering “imaginaries for the unfamiliar realm of the future” (8). Mayerson, in his empirical study of the impact of climate fiction on readers, provides case-based evidence to support this position. Making use of Kahneman and Tversky’s concept of ‘simulation heuristic’, a psychological principle which argues that people’s ability to imagine an occurrence condition their willfulness to perceive its possibilities, he argues that climate fiction, by offering concrete images of possible futures bring credibility to the otherwise vague data of science (Mayerson 2018, 487).

The assertions in favour of climate fiction’s ability to negotiate the complexities of climate change and its utility to influence public opinion are contested. Craps and Crownshaw, for instance, observe that climate fiction’s inclination towards futuristic plots can distract public attention from the mundane, uneven distribution of climate vulnerabilities (5). Shelley Streeby makes a vital intervention in this context by pointing out how the imaginary of climate fiction excludes indigenous communities and people of colour (4-5). Mayerson concurs by observing that “the majority of characters in recent American climate change fiction have been wealthy, American, white, cisgendered heterosexual males...[who can be] more accurately described as the perpetrators than the primary victims of the “slow violence” of climate change” (Mayerson 2017, 317). Caracciolo et al., remarks that climate fiction is generally expected to address questions of “subjectivity, agency, personhood, materiality, and embodiment”, but it fails

very often to stand up to the challenge, because of limiting the scope of text to merely using climate change as thematic backdrop “while foregrounding relatively conventional characters and situations” (8-9).

A similar critical position questions the utility of apocalyptic tropes that are frequently employed by writers of climate fiction. Mayerson notes that the purported use of “post apocalyptic landscapes” to caution readers of climatic consequences and thereby provoke ethical environmental responses can be counterproductive as readers might simply ignore such tropes owing to decades of exposure to apocalyptic scenarios offered by science fiction writers (Mayerson 2017, 315). In his empirical study on the influence of climate fiction on readers, Mayerson reinforces this idea by stating that the “disaster frame” commonly used by climate fiction, which perpetuates the idea that climate change “can only be addressed by loss, cost and sacrifice” can backfire as it creates a sense of helplessness that disempower and demobilize the reader from assuming a more responsive or proactive sociopolitical position to confront the challenges of climate change (Mayerson 2018, 489-491). Whiteley et al., while critiquing Atwood’s *Oryx and Crake*, notes that dystopian, post apocalyptic plots that are telescopically placed in the far future can be counterintuitive to the function of climate fiction as it offers no solutions for “the challenges of living with the ravages of climate change” in the present (35).

One of the most arbitrated questions is related to the viability of fiction in representing a phenomenon of vast temporal and spatial dimension like climate change. Tuhus-Dubrow, for instance, observes that the slow-time human experience of climate change and its reckoning as a phenomenon that implicates collective as well as individual way of living are not “conducive to dramatic plot” (61). Trexler and Johns-Putra, while pointing out the immensity of climate change’s temporality and spatiality, acknowledges that the scientific premises of climate change itself involves a certain degree of imprecision with respect to its extent

and speed that contributes to “public confusion, controversy, and skepticism, which is sometimes quick to construe scientific imprecision as uncertainty and even conspiracy” (185). Goodbody and Johns-Putra similarly speak of climate change as an unpresentable phenomenon on account of its invisibility. Quoting Sheila Jasanoff, they observe that the science of climate change, which depend on “techniques of aggregation and deletion, calculation and comparison...exhaust the capacities of even the most meticulously recorded communal memories”. This situates the writer of climate fiction within what Timothy Clark calls the “Anthropocene disorder, a...demand to think of human life at much broader scales of space and time” (234-235).

There are other propositions that question the propriety of climate fiction in the context of climate change. Craps and Crownshaw reveal a paradoxical position in climate fiction’s seeming function of serving an ecological cause by situating the origin of its parent form, the novel, within capitalism. Quoting Stephanie Le Menager, they point out how “the novel has always been enabled by economic and industrial systems of modernity and their resources” and climate fiction therefore is the “materialization of the very environmental histories it represents” (2). Sperling expresses similar misgivings about the appropriateness of novel in the addressing questions of climate crises as she apperceives it as a form that was “complicit...in processes that lead to climate crises” (17).

An allowance for these critical positions conceded, it shall be meaningful to perform an analysis of how Maja Lunde’s *The History of Bees* (2015) mediates questions pertaining to the efficacy of climate fiction in the context of climate change. The first of the four novels, that constitute her climate quartet, the others being *The End of the Ocean* (2017), *The Last Wild Horses* (2019) and *The Dream of a Tree* (2022), (the years in parenthesis correspond to the publication date of original titles in Norwegian), the novel narrates three different stories, located in three spatio-temporal settings, the story of Tao taking place in 2098, Sichuan,

China, the story William taking place in 1851, Hertfordshire, England and the story of George, taking place in 2007, Ohio, USA. While these stories may seem apparently disconnected from each other, they are connected by an invisible thread that constitutes the history of apiculture, the mass disappearance of bees due to what is termed as Colony Collapse Disorder (CCD) (*The History of Bees*⁷⁵, 232) and the hope of their eventual return.

Lunde's novel, right from the outset, seemingly negates questions regarding the efficacy of novel to address the vast temporal and spatial dimension of climate change by dividing the plot into three spatio-temporal settings that cover a history (futuristic projection included) of 248 years and spaces of England, USA, China and briefly Australia. Tuhus-Dubrow's skepticism that the slow-time human experience of climate change and its reckoning as a phenomenon that implicates collective as well as individual way of living are not "conducive to dramatic plot" finds arbitration as Lunde, from the story of William in 1851, who overcomes a state of depression and turns to apiculture having found inspiration from François Huber's *New Observations on the Natural History of Bees* (61) through the story of George, a beekeeper with a respectable number of 324 hives (327), to the story a Tao, who works as a hand pollinator in a world without bees (1), traces a slow-time history of how bees, that were natural to world in the past, are apparently tamed by humanity in the present, and owing to the excessive use of pesticides dwindle in number, that too in a way inconspicuous to the human eye, until the "mysterious colony collapses" as noted by George begins in the southern states of USA like Florida and California, eventually culminating in 2045, when "there were no bees left on the planet" (291).

The observation made by Craps and Crownshaw that climate fiction's inclination towards futuristic plots can distract public attention from the mundane, uneven distribution of climate vulnerabilities and Shelley Streeby's incrimination that climate fiction excludes indigenous communities and people of colour are effectively negotiated by Lunde as the brunt of the vulnerability

question are born by the people of Asia, represented by Tao, Kuan and their six year old boy Wei Wen, who dies of the sting of a bee that makes reappearance after five decades of absence. The consequences of Western agricultural practices that rely on the heavy use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides are faced by the people of China as the declining number of bees pushes their existence to the margins of survival. Lunde uses several instances to affectively register the vulnerability enforced upon the Chinese, including the hunger of Wei Wen, whose dietary needs are compromised (19-20), Tao and Kuan sacrificing their share of plums for their child (68), the modest menu of the restaurant visited by Tao in Beijing which serves only fried rice, the condition of the impoverished father and son who runs it (180), the three teenagers who are helplessly pushed onto the verge of cannibalism owing to their deprivation, yet are not completely driven of their capacity for understanding and compassion (221-223) and more importantly the general decay that has affected the civilization, marked by decrepitude, depopulation and desertification. A notable instance is the way Tao describes Beijing as a city that “had grown and developed to a certain point, then...had come to a halt, and was now deteriorating. Like an old person approaching death. More and more alone, more and more quiet, at a pace that slowed with every passing day” (180).

It is significant to note that descriptive words like ‘dry’, ‘barren’ (172), ‘deserted’ (182, 220, 224) etc. which makes several appearances in Tao’s story are contrasted with descriptions of lush greenery and fruitfulness in both William’s and George’s narratives. William, for instance, describes “The leaves were an intense play of colors, clear yellow, warm brown, blood red...Nature was brimming with fruit, trees laden with apples, juicy plums, dripping sugary pears” (26) and George recalls “Blueberry bushes in bloom are beautiful things...every time Maine greeted me with its white and pink knolls in May, I just had to stop and look. It was so beautiful that books should be written about it”. George’s further remark that “without bees, the flowers were just flowers. Not blueberries, not bread and butter” (162)

powerfully captures the fact that what is lost for the future world of Tao is attributed to the extinction of bees, due to the recklessness of the Western world. Lunde subtly smuggles several hints that speaks of the drivers of global capitalism at work in both George's and Tao's story, namely the appearance of the word 'plastic' (1, 172, 188, 218, 244), 'helicopter' (81), "a huge German SUV" (90), "the cheap trashy electronics" (111), "a green pick up and a black SUV", "a huge Chevrolet" (233) etc., all meant to draw attention to the various vectors that lead the world ecology to its progressive collapse.

Mayerson's skeptical inference that climate fiction's frequent dependency on "postapocalyptic landscapes" to caution readers of climatic consequences would be counterproductive as the "disaster frame" would create a sense of helplessness that disempower and demobilize the reader does not hold for Lunde's novel as the two-third of its narrative dwells in a more or less realistic past and present compared to the one third of the story set in the future. As for Tao's story set in 2098, it is worth noting that Lunde discards the drama of apocalyptic trope in favour of a matter-of-fact narration that relies mostly on the imagined consequences of much anticipated and scientifically valid anxiety surrounding Colony Collapse Disorder and the extinction of bees. The only episode that fits the apocalyptic canvas perhaps is the one that deals with Tao's visit to Beijing to unravel the mystery of her son Wei Wen. But there too, it is evident that Lunde remains focused on the consequentiality of a world without pollination as images of desolation, deprivation and decay that largely loom over the city are related to systemic failure of a political economic framework built upon agriculture. For instance, Tao while recalling her past makes a distinction between times before and after the collapse. The world before the collapse is presented through a contemporary lens when "technology had made everything available. Availability was the mantra of that period" in stark contrast to the time after the collapse when "the democracies fell...the world war...followed, when food became a commodity bestowed upon only a select few" (22).

Finally, Sperling's misgivings about novel as a form that was "complicit...in processes that lead to climate crises" and the consideration of Craps and Crownshaw's proposition that novel as a literary form originated from within capitalist modes of production can also be negated as Lunde's novel exhibits characteristics of posthumanism by moving beyond questions of human exceptionalism and attributing centrality or agency to the bees. Two critical posthumanist ideas foregrounded by Caracciolo et.al. in their posthumanist survey of climate fiction might be of help to clarify this position. On one hand they quote Serenella Iovino's proposal "to move "past the human,"... "not so much that of debunking the human altogether, but rather that of discarding the dogma of human exceptionalism"" and on the other hand Serpil Oppermann's assertion of the need for a critical standpoint that consider "the nonhuman (biotic and abiotic) as already part of the human in the world's becoming" (10). *The History of Bees* is performative of these theoretical positions as bees occupy a central position around which the lives of William, George, Tao and others unfold and develop. George realises this dependency multiple times in the novel, for instance he says that "agriculture", the source of everyone's sustenance "didn't have a chance without bees" (90) and later "without bees, the flowers were just flowers" (162). A victim of the collapse, Tao recognizes the agency of the bees better as she says "without bees thousands of acres of cultivated fields suddenly lay fallow. Flowering fields without berries, trees without fruit" (274). Towards the end, she reckons the humility of the human subjective position within the nexus of inter-species relationship further when she observes that "bees cannot be tamed. They can only be tended, receive our care" (334).

To conclude, *The History of Bees* is an epistemic exploration of humanity's relationship with bees, beginning with their anatomical curiosity in the insect, followed by discovery of its economic value, attempt to domesticate them and eventually driving them to the verge of extinction. Maja Lunde, blending facts and fiction, effectively traces this genealogy using selective markers, beginning with Jan Swammerdam, the Dutch biologist and

microscopist, whose curious exploration into the anatomy of the insect in his work *Biblia Naturae* forms William's entry as a young naturalist into the world of bees, followed by the Swiss entomologist François Huber's *New Observations on the Natural History of Bees*, which inspires William with the idea that bees can be domesticated (61-64), William's pursuit at designing his own unique model of hive and his correspondence with the Polish vicar and beekeeper Johann Dzierzon, his short-lived triumph of developing Savage's Standard Hive (266) and further disillusionment and death, Charlotte's, his daughter, journey to USA and becoming the great grandmother of George, thereby handing over the beekeeping tradition, George's confrontation with the Colony Collapse Disorder and ultimately his son Thomas Savage's fictitious book "The History of Bees" published in 2037, (327) which inspires Tao, both to come in terms with her son's death as well as act as a brave mother, who embraces her son's death as a signifier of the return of bees, which gives humanity the hope of survival. Maja Lunde, casting behind much of the criticism faced by earlier works of climate fiction, presents *The History of Bees* as a prototype that offers new ways of confronting the crises by finding a balance between the facts of science and the affective possibilities of representing it in fiction.

Works Cited

- Caracciolo, Marco, et al. "Climate Fiction: A Posthumanist Survey." *Interférences littéraires /Literaire interferences*, edited by Marieke Winkler, Marjolein van Herten, and Jilt Jorritsma, no. 27, Nov. 2022, pp. 6–21.
- Craps, Stef, and Rick Crownshaw. "Introduction: The Rising Tide of Climate Change Fiction." *Studies in the Novel*, vol. 50, no. 1, Spring 2018, pp. 1–8.
- Goodbody, Axel, and Adeline Johns-Putra. "The Rise of the Climate Change Novel." *Climate and Literature*, edited by Adeline Johns-Putra, Cambridge University Press, 2019, pp. 229–245.

- Lunde, Maja. *The History of Bees*. Translated by Diane Oatley, Scribner, 2017.
- Macfarlane, Robert. "The Burning Question." *The Guardian*, 24 Sept. 2005. www.theguardian.com/books/2005/sep/24/featuresreviews.guardianreview29
- Mehnert, Antonia. *Climate Change Fictions: Representations of Global Warming in American Literature*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2016.
- Schneider-Mayerson, Matthew. "Climate Change Fiction." *American Literature in Transition, 2000–2010*, edited by Rachel Greenwald Smith, Cambridge University Press, 2017, pp. 309–321.
- . "The Influence of Climate Fiction: An Empirical Survey of Readers." *Environmental Humanities*, vol. 10, no. 2, Nov. 2018, pp. 474–500. doi:10.1215/22011919-7156848.
- Sperling, Alison. "Climate Fictions: An Introduction." *Paradoxa*, no. 31, 2019-20, pp. 7–21.
- Streeby, Shelley. *Imagining the Future of Climate Change: World-Making through Science Fiction and Activism*. University of California Press, 2018.
- Trexler, Adam, and Adeline Johns-Putra. "Climate Change in Literature and Literary Criticism." *WIREs Climate Change*, vol. 2, no. 2, Mar.–Apr. 2011, pp. 185–200. doi.org/10.1002/wcc.105.
- Tuhus-Dubrow, Rebecca. "Cli-Fi: Birth of a Genre." *Dissent*, vol. 60, no. 3, Summer 2013, University of Pennsylvania Press, pp. 58–61. doi:10.1353/dss.2013.0069.
- Whiteley, Andrea, et al. "Climate Change Imaginaries? Examining Expectation Narratives in Cli-Fi Novels." *Bulletin of Science, Technology & Society*, 2016, doi:10.1177/0270467615622845.